

Benchmarking FRENETIC and FENNECS in the Simulation of Compensated Reactor Transients

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a code-to-code comparison between the deterministic codes FRENETIC and FENNECS in the time-dependent framework by simulating so-called *compensated transients* in thermal and fast neutron spectrum reactor models. This kind of transient is initiated by sudden interchanges of materials in such a way that the static reactivity remains unaffected while the spatial distributions of, e.g., neutron flux and power density as well as the dynamic reactivity undergoes substantial changes. This transient is modelled using both the predictor-corrector quasi-static method (FRENETIC) and the fully implicit direct integration method (FRENETIC and FENNECS) of the diffusion equation. The neutron flux in steady state and its time evolutions computed by the two codes present in general good agreements.

Keywords: Quasi-static method, fully implicit method, nuclear reactor dynamics, FRENETIC, FENNECS

1. INTRODUCTION

The simulation of transient and accidental scenarios in nuclear reactors requires an accurate numerical solution of the time-dependent Boltzmann transport equation. Fully implicit direct time discretization and transport approximations lead to a sequence of fixed-source problems with time-dependent sources at each time step, whose repeated solution can be computationally demanding. The quasi-static method [1, 2] offers an efficient alternative to mitigate this cost. In this study, both the fully implicit and the predictor-corrector quasi-static schemes implemented in the nodal diffusion code FRENETIC, which offers an adaptive time-step control, are compared with the fully implicit approach of the finite-element diffusion code FENNECS. This work extends a previous steady-state comparison between the two codes [3], representing a first step towards a detailed assessment of the quasi-static method against fully implicit solutions under representative transient conditions.

In this section, a brief summary of the problem setup is given, starting with the within-group time-dependent diffusion equation (see, e. g., [4]):

$$\frac{1}{v_g} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \phi_g(\vec{r}) - \vec{\nabla} \cdot \left(D_g(\vec{r}) \vec{\nabla} \phi_g(\vec{r}, t) \right) + \Sigma_g^r(\vec{r}) \phi_g(\vec{r}, t) = s_g(\vec{r}, t). \quad (1)$$

Therein, standard symbols and notation are used as in classic references (see, e.g. [5]) with g and l indexing the energy group and the delayed neutron precursor group, $\Sigma_g^r(\vec{r}) = \Sigma_g^{tot}(\vec{r}) - \Sigma_{gg}^{scatt}(\vec{r})$ being the removal cross section and

$$s_g(\vec{r}, t) = \chi_g \sum_{g'} v \Sigma_{g'}^{fiss}(\vec{r}) \phi_{g'}(\vec{r}, t) + \sum_{g' \neq g} \Sigma_{gg'}^{scatt}(\vec{r}) \phi_{g'}(\vec{r}, t) + \frac{1}{v_g \Delta t} \phi_g(\vec{r}, t) + \frac{1}{\Delta t} \sum_l \chi_{gl}^d \lambda_l \gamma_l c_l(\vec{r}, t)$$

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being the sum of fission source, scattering source and time-dependent source (last two terms) of energy group g with the abbreviation $\gamma_l = \frac{\Delta t}{1+\lambda_l \Delta t}$. The fully implicit time discretization is obtained by integrating Eq. (1) over a single time step $\Delta t = t^{\tau+1} - t^\tau$ and evaluating the resulting integrals by their respective integrands at the upper end of this time step¹. This results in the following fixed-source problem to be solved at each time step:

$$D_g(\vec{r})\Delta\phi_g^{\tau+1}(\vec{r}) + \tilde{\Sigma}_g^{tot}(\vec{r})\phi_g^{\tau+1}(\vec{r}) = s_g^\tau(\vec{r}) \quad (2)$$

with

$$s_g^\tau(\vec{r}) = \tilde{\chi}_g \sum_{g'} \nu \Sigma_{g'}^{fiss}(\vec{r}) \phi_{g'}^\tau(\vec{r}) + \sum_{g' \neq g} \Sigma_{gg'}^{scatt}(\vec{r}) \phi_{g'}^\tau(\vec{r}) + \frac{1}{v_g \Delta t} \phi_g^\tau(\vec{r}) + \frac{1}{\Delta t} \sum_l \chi_{gl}^d \lambda_l \gamma_l c_l^\tau(\vec{r}).$$

In Eq. (2),

$$\tilde{\Sigma}_g^{tot}(\vec{r}) = \Sigma_g^{tot}(\vec{r}) + \frac{1}{v_g \Delta t}, \quad \tilde{\chi}_g = \chi_g(1 - \beta) + \sum_l \chi_{gl}^d \lambda_l \gamma_l \beta_l.$$

The main advantage of the fully implicit approach lies in its unconditional numerical stability, independent of the chosen time-step size, which is limited only by the convergence behaviour and the desired accuracy. However, solving Eq. (2) requires the inversion of the transport operator, which entails a computational cost comparable to that of a steady-state eigenvalue problem. The quasi-static method alleviates this burden by assuming that the neutron flux $\phi(\vec{r}, E, t)$ can be factorized into an amplitude function $T(t)$, representing the overall reactor power, and a shape function $\psi(\vec{r}, E, t)$, accounting for the spatial and spectral distribution evolving on a slower time scale:

$$\phi(\vec{r}, E, t) = T(t)\psi(\vec{r}, E, t). \quad (3)$$

This factorization enables separate treatments of the amplitude and shape on their respective time scales. In particular, the predictor–corrector quasi-static (PCQM) method updates the amplitude through frequent, low-cost evaluations, while the shape is recomputed only when significant deviations occur. The adaptive time-step control further enhances robustness and efficiency, making the algorithm well suited for accurately capturing reactor transients at a reduced computational cost.

The next section gives a short summary of the neutron kinetics codes FRENETIC and FENNECS, while in section 3.2 we present the results obtained with the two codes considering two reactor specifications, one with a thermal and the other with a fast neutron spectrum. Finally, some conclusions and future perspective are provided in 4.

2. DESCRIPTIONS OF THE MULTIGROUP NEUTRON KINETICS CODES

This section provides short descriptions of the nodal code FRENETIC that implements the quasi-static method and the finite element code FENNECS that applies a fully implicit time discretization.

2.1. The Neutron Kinetics Code FRENETIC

FRENETIC (Fast REactor Neutronics/Thermal-hydraulICS) is a multiphysics code developed at Politecnico di Torino for the simulation of steady-state and transient behaviour of liquid metal-cooled fast reactor cores arranged in hexagonal closed assemblies. The code couples a few-group neutron diffusion model with one-dimensional advection–diffusion thermal–hydraulic equations for each assembly, accounting for inter-assembly heat exchange [6]. The neutronic module adopts a three-dimensional coarse-mesh nodal expansion method, where each sub-assembly is represented by vertically stacked

¹Evaluating the integrands at the beginning or mid of the time step corresponds to explicit and semi-implicit discretization, respectively.

hexagonal prisms with one radial node per assembly. Fourth- and third-order polynomials are used to represent the flux in the radial and axial directions, respectively, ensuring local neutron balance in each node. This approach enables full-core NE–TH calculations at reduced computational cost while maintaining adequate accuracy for design and safety analyses. The neutronic module implements the fully implicit time discretisation scheme as well as improved versions of the quasi-static method, equipped with an adaptive time-step selection [7]. FRENETIC is written in Fortran 90 and provides Python bindings for automated input generation, execution, and post-processing. In the present study, FRENETIC 2.1 was applied.

2.2. The Neutron Kinetics Code FENNECS

The *Finite ElemeNt NEutroniCS* code FENNECS is a few-group neutron kinetics code with fully implicit time discretization based on the finite element method [8, 9]. Through its geometric flexibility, FENNECS can handle the more complex geometries of Small Modular Reactors (SMR) and, in particular, Micro Modular Reactors (MMRs) with rotating control drums and other innovative concepts including Generation IV designs. The geometric flexibility of FENNECS is accomplished by a Galerkin weighted residual finite element approach for the diffusion and the Simplified P_3 (SP_3) transport equation [10]. Starting with the implementation of a steady state diffusion solver, FENNECS has been continuously extended by numerous features, e. g., couplings with the GRS system code ATHLET and the subchannel code CTF, the implementation of the discontinuous Galerkin approach with Assembly Discontinuity Factors (ADF) [11], the capability to simulate rotating control drums [12] etc. For the spatial meshing of the problem geometry, including control drums peculiar for MMRs, the accompanied *Python External Meshing Tool with Yaml input* (PEMTY) is developed and applied. Since 2023, FENNECS is a module of the GRS reactor simulation code package AC^2 [13] consisting of the major components ATHLET, ATHLET-CD and COCOSYS. The latest release of AC^2 , named AC^2 -2025, has been published recently. In the present study, FENNECS 1.13.6 was applied.

3. COMPENSATED TRANSIENT

The transients analysed in this work belong to the class of the so-called *compensated transients*, initiated by an instantaneous change in the reactor configuration that, by design, preserves the overall criticality condition. Although such an event is neither physically feasible nor operationally meaningful, it represents a particularly challenging test case from a modelling perspective, as it involves a sharp variation in the system's dynamic reactivity caused by the mismatch between the flux shape and the modified core layout.

From a static standpoint, the multiplication factor — and thus the static reactivity — remains unchanged. However, the sudden material swap alters the spatial distribution of cross sections, thereby affecting both the instantaneous reactivity and the power evolution. As a result, the neutron flux and the delayed neutron precursor fields evolve dynamically to reach a new equilibrium consistent with the updated reactor configuration, with the radial and axial flux distributions simply interchanged with respect to the initial condition.

This class of transients is particularly relevant because it induces significant spatial distortions of the neutron flux, which cannot be captured by point-kinetics models and therefore require space–time approaches such as quasi-static or fully implicit direct integration schemes.

3.1. Compensated Transient in a Reactor with Thermal Neutron Spectrum

The reactor with thermal neutron spectrum considered in this subsection is adopted from Ref. [14] and depicted in Fig. 1 on the left. It consists of a regular lattice of 37 hexagonal fuel assemblies arranged in three rings around a central fuel assembly. The lattice flat-to-flat pitch is 20 cm, and the axial extension

of the core amounts to 80 cm. The core is represented by only two materials, whose two-group data are given in Table I. Only one delayed neutron precursor family is considered. Axially, the core is divided into two equally sized regions, the lower one consisting of material 1, the upper one of material 2. Radially, half of the fuel assemblies is composed of material 1, the other half of material 2, except for the central assembly which is axially homogeneous and consists of material 1. Vacuum boundary conditions, i. e., zero incoming neutron flux, are applied at all external reactor boundaries. Fig. 1 on the right depicts the meshing and material distribution in FENNECS.

To carry out a preliminary comparison between the codes, a quite coarse and constant time step size of $\Delta t = 0.01$ s is adopted. A total problem time of 1.5 s is considered which requires 150 time steps. The transient problem time is divided into three equally sized time intervals, each lasting for 0.5 s. During the first third of the transient, the reactor state remains unchanged. Within the next time step, i. e., at $t = 0.5$ s + Δt , an instantaneous material swap happens, i. e., materials 1 and 2 are interchanged, before the second third of the transient follows with no changes to the (swapped) reactor state. At $t = 1.0$ s + Δt , a second material swap takes place, thereby turning the reactor back to its initial state. During the last third of the transient, no further changes to the reactor state happens. Table II summarizes the sequence of events.

Figure 1. Initial configuration of the reactor (left) and its meshing of the two axial sections in FENNECS (center, right). Labels of the form l/u ($l \in \{1, 2\}$) indicate the material assigned to the lower (l) and upper (u) axial zone of each fuel assembly except for the central one which consist of material 1. Fast reactor: $z_{1/2} = 40$ cm, $z_{top} = 80$ cm, $p = 20$ cm; thermal reactor: $z_{1/2} = 50$ cm, $z_{top} = 100$ cm, $p = 21.51$ cm

Table I. Group constants for the thermal spectrum reactor. $\lambda = 0.08$ 1/s and $\beta = 0.0075$.

Material	Group g	v_g (cm/s)	D_g (cm)	$\nu\Sigma_{fg}$ (1/cm)	χ_g	$\Sigma_{g \rightarrow 1}$ (1/cm)	$\Sigma_{g \rightarrow 2}$ (1/cm)
1	1	$1.0 \cdot 10^7$	1.5	0.01	1.0	0.196222222	0.015
	2	$3.0 \cdot 10^5$	0.5	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.486666667
2	1	$1.0 \cdot 10^7$	1.5	0.005	1.0	0.313333333	0.01
	2	$3.0 \cdot 10^5$	0.5	0.099	0.0	0.0	0.586666667

3.2. Compensated Transient in a Reactor with Fast Neutron Spectrum

The geometry of the fast reactor considered in the following is a slight modification of the specifications given in Section 3.1. The assembly flat-to-flat pitch is 21.51 cm and the axial extension of the core is 100 cm. Material 1 is represented by the fuel of the middle axial section of the inner core, material 2 by the fuel of the middle axial section of the outer core of the ALFRED lead-cooled fast reactor concept (LEADER design [15]). The cross sections have been generated by the Monte Carlo code Serpent [16]

Table II. Sequence of events in the reactor with thermal ($t_1 = 0.5$ s, $t_2 = 1.0$ s, $t_3 = 1.5$ s, $\Delta t = 0.01$ s) and fast neutron spectrum ($t_1 = 0.001$ s, $t_2 = 0.002$ s, $t_3 = 0.003$ s, $\Delta t = 1.0 \cdot 10^{-7}$ s).

Time	Event
$0 \text{ s} \leq t \leq t_1$	No changes to reactor state
$t_1 + \Delta t$	Instantaneous material swap
$t_1 + \Delta t < t \leq t_2$	No changes to reactor state
$t_2 + \Delta t$	Instantaneous material swap
$t_2 + \Delta t < t \leq t_3$	No changes to reactor state

in 6 energy groups and 6 delayed neutron precursor families. The sequence of events is similar to the transient in the thermal reactor, except for the time step size being now $1 \cdot 10^{-7}$ s and the total transient problem time of 0.003 s requiring 30000 time steps. The reason for selecting this time step size is to be able to resolve the neutron dynamic which is governed by a neutron generation time of about $4 \cdot 10^{-7}$ s typical for liquid metal cooled reactors. Refer to Table II for details.

Figure 2. Total power evolutions predicted by the two codes for the thermal (left) and fast reactor (right) cases.

Figure 3. Time snapshot of the flux axial shape in selected fuel assemblies at $t = 2$ ms for the 5th (left) and 6th (right) groups. Both codes employ the fully implicit direct time scheme.

Figure 4. Time snapshot of the flux axial shape in selected fuel assemblies at $t = 2$ ms for energy groups 5 (left) and 6 (right). The FRENETIC results are computed with the PCQM.

Figure 5. Time snapshot of the flux axial shape in selected fuel assemblies at $t = 3$ ms for energy groups 5 (left) and 6 (right). The FRENETIC results are obtained by the PCQM.

3.3. Numerical results

The simulations presented in the following were performed using the same number of axial elements — 20 uniformly spaced bins for the fast case and 8 for the thermal case — consistent with the discretization adopted in [14]. Owing to intrinsic differences in the spatial schemes of the two codes, the same logic could not be applied to the radial mesh. In particular, FRENETIC employs a single node per assembly. Consequently, the FENNECS mesh was defined to match the FRENETIC mesh as closely as possible, discretizing the hexagonal assembly into six elements, i.e., one per edge.

As discussed earlier, the time step adopted for the fast case with the fully implicit direct integration scheme was set to 10^{-7} s. This value represents a reasonable compromise between the prompt time scale ($\approx 3 \times 10^{-7}$ s for this system) and computational cost.

Figure 2 illustrates the time evolution of the total reactor power as computed by the two codes in the two compensated transient scenarios. The overall agreement is satisfactory, although FENNECS exhibits a slight deviation between 0 and 1.5 ms. It has been shown that the magnitude of this slight (approx. 0.3 %) drop of the power level becomes smaller if the steady state convergence criteria are tightened. Following the first reactor swap at $t = 1$ ms, the power undergoes a prompt decrease before stabilizing at a lower level. After the second swap, the power returns to its initial value. The two spikes observed at the swap instants correspond to the prompt response of the neutron population to the transient perturbation caused by the core material exchange. Regarding computational demands, a single time step in FENNECS requires a little less than half a second. This amounts to about 3.7 hours of CPU time for the 30000 time steps of the whole transient simulation, vs. 1.3 hours of FRENETIC, which requires a

time between 0.5 and 0.05 s to simulate one time step.

Figure 3 compares the axial flux profiles in selected fuel assemblies (numbering as in Figure 1) at representative time snapshots and energy groups, as computed using the fully implicit direct integration scheme in both codes. Comparable results are shown in Figure 4 and Figure 5, where FENNECS outcomes are compared with those obtained using the PCQM approach in FRENETIC. Overall, the agreement between the codes is very good in both cases, with the largest—though still limited—deviation observed in the central assembly. For brevity, the comparison of the fluxes in the thermal case is not shown here as it exhibits a qualitatively similar behaviour.

4. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study presented a comparative analysis of transient simulations using the nodal diffusion code FRENETIC and the finite-element diffusion code FENNECS, focusing on the challenging case of compensated transients in reactors with thermal and fast neutron spectra. The results showed very good overall agreement between the two codes, confirming the robustness of both the fully implicit and the predictor–corrector quasi-static (PCQM) approaches. Minor discrepancies observed in the early phase of the fast transient point to aspects that merit further investigation, particularly concerning spatial coupling and time-step sensitivity.

Future developments will include a systematic sensitivity analysis on the time-step size and spatial discretization adopted in FENNECS, with particular attention to the computational performance of both codes. Emphasis will be placed on quantifying the efficiency gains of the quasi-static method relative to the fully implicit scheme and on exploring adaptive strategies for space–time resolution in coupled multiphysics simulations.

In the longer term, the methodology will be extended to more realistic transient scenarios, including reactivity insertions and feedback effects, to further assess the accuracy and applicability of the proposed approaches.

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